

The Effect of Conflict and Termination of Employment on Employee's Work Spirit

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to find out the conflict and termination of employment both partially and simultaneously have a significant effect on the morale of employees at PT. The benefits of Medan Technique and how much it affects. The method used in this research is quantitative method with several tests namely *reliability analysis*, classical assumption deviation test and *linear regression*. Based on the results of primary data regression processed using SPSS 20, multiple linear regression equations were obtained as follows: $Y = 1,031 + 0.329 X_1 + 0.712 X_2$. In part, the conflict variable (X_1) has a significant effect on the employee's work spirit (Y) at PT. Medan Technical Benefits. This means that the hypothesis in this study was accepted, proven from the value of t calculate $> t$ table ($3,952 < 2,052$). While the variable termination of employment (X_2) has a significant influence on the work spirit of employees (Y) in PT. Medan Technical Benefits. This means that the hypothesis in this study was accepted, proven from the value of t calculate $> t$ table ($7,681 > 2,052$). Simultaneously, variable conflict (X_1) and termination of employment (X_2) have a significant influence on the morale of employees (Y) in PT. Medan Technical Benefits. This means that the hypothesis in this study was accepted, as evidenced by the calculated F value $> F$ table ($221,992 > 3.35$). Conflict variables (X_1) and termination of employment (X_2) were able to contribute an influence on employee morale variables (Y) of 94.3% while the remaining 5.7% was influenced by other variables not studied in this study. From the above conclusions, the author advises that employees and leaders should reduce prolonged conflict so that the spirit of work can increase. Leaders should be more selective in severing employment relationships so that decent employees are not dismissed unilaterally. Employees should work in a high spirit so that the company can see the quality that employees have.

KEYWORDS: Conflict, Termination of Employment, and Employee Spirit of Employment

INTRODUCTION

Conflicts can occur due to differences in thought and purpose. Differences of thought can be seen from the different backgrounds of a person and his culture. A person will be influenced by the mindsets and establishment of his group. Those different thoughts and establishments will eventually result in differences in character and individuals that can trigger conflict.

Conflict is a matter of communication between individuals and groups. If the relationship in communication between individuals and groups is not going well, then most likely communication relationships on a larger scale will not go well. In communicating it is necessary to understand and convey information that can be received by a person clearly.

In any organization or company, dissent is often intentional or unintentional, one of the strategies of leaders to make changes and to see how far an employee can resolve the conflict. Conflicts can occur due to personal problems brought in at work that lead to misunderstandings with other coworking friends so as to trigger conflict.

The effect of a conflict is discomfort in work, the inconvenience of an employee will cause a decrease in work that will personally impact the quality of his work. In addition, it will trigger employees to stop to work. Many companies take this opportunity to make changes by termination of employment to employees who have conflicts both personally and in groups.

Termination of employment provided will adversely affect the employee, resulting in his economic status. In addition to the conflict, the termination of employment was done because the company experienced a decrease in sales or there were internal problems that had to be termination of employment of some employees.

Pt. Medan Technical Benefits is a company engaged in construction equipment and agriculture. Pt. Medan Technical Benefits has 90% male employees both warehouse and transportation. In its activities PT. The benefits of Medan Engineering

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experienced several problems related to conflict and termination of employment that resulted in a decrease in the morale of employees. Based on the author's observation that conflict management in PT. The benefits of Medan Techniques have not been optimal so that the employee's morale decreases. There is no guarantee of the quality of goods related to the goods delivered, if the goods delivered are damaged in the journey then the responsible drivers and employees, and if not able to replace then the driver and employees will be fired without any severance.

Research Objectives

A study must have a purpose, as for the general purpose of this research are:

1. To know the conflict and termination of employment both partially and simultaneously has a significant effect on the spirit of work of employees in PT. Medan Technical Benefits.
2. To know the effect of conflict and termination of employment on the spirit of employee work in PT. Medan Technical Benefits.

THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

A. Conflict

According to Mangkunegara (2013:155) argues that "Conflict is a conflict that occurs between what a person expects against himself, others, the organization with the reality of what is expected". According to Sedarmayanti (2019:279) argues that "Conflict usually arises in an organization as a result of various problems in terms of communication, personal relationships or due to organizational structure problems".

According to Stephen P. Robbins (in Fahmi, 2016:292) defines conflict as a process by which a person makes a deliberate attempt to eliminate the efforts of others by an attempt to obstruct and thus frustrates others in attempting to achieve his or her goals or in continuing his interests. According to Luthans, F (in Fahmi, 2016:292) defines conflict as a mismatch of value or purpose between members of an organization. Whereas according to DuBrin, A. I (in Fahmi, 2016:292) defines conflict as referring to conflict between individuals or groups that can increase tensions as a result of mutual obstruction in achieving goals. According to T. Hani Handoko (in Fahmi, 2016:292) in nature conflict can be defined as any kind of conflict or antagonistic interaction between two or more parties. Furthermore, T. Hani Handoko said about organizational conflicts, namely; *organizational conflict is a discrepancy between two or more members or organizational groups arising from the fact that they have to share limited resources or work activities or due to the fact that they have different status, goals, values or perceptions.*

B. Termination of Employment

According to Mangkunegara (in Hamali, 2018:250) termination of employment (layoffs) or dismissal of employees is a temporary or permanent termination of employment carried out by the company at the request of employees or because of the will of the company. The purpose of employee dismissal is to maintain the effectiveness and efficiency of the company's organization. According to Hasibuan (2009:209) argues that "Termination is the termination of a person's employment with an employment organization. With the dismissal, it means the end of employees' work attachment to the company".

According to Sedarmayanti (2019:403) argues that "Termination of employment (layoffs) is a condition of no longer working employees in a company because the working relationship between the company is severed, or not extended anymore". According to Sofyandi (in Supomo, 2019:148) dismissal is the process of termination of an employee's employment with an organization / company.

According to the Government (in Supomo, 2019:148) dismissal is the dismissal of employees or employees in the organizational environment. It must be in accordance with Government Regulation, namely Law No. 12 of 1964 of the Criminal Code and the permission of P4D or P4P or by a court decision. Based on the above understanding, it can be concluded that the termination of employment of employees based on their own desires or the company is caused by mistakes.

C. Work Spirit

According to Nitisemito (in Laksarini, 2018:22) the definition of work spirit is the condition of a person who supports himself to do work faster and better in the company. The spirit of work is also an individual or group's attitude towards his volunteerism to work together in order to devote his ability thoroughly. Whereas According to Hasibuan (in Laksarini, 2018:22) The spirit of work is the desire and seriousness of a person to do his job well and be disciplined to achieve maximum work achievement.

Sastrohadiwiryono (in Laksarini, 2018:23) describes the spirit of work as a spiritual condition, or the behavior of individual labor and groups that cause deep pleasure in the workforce to work diligently and consequently in achieving the goals set by the

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company. Based on the above opinion, it can be concluded that the spirit of work is a positive energy that is present in an employee.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research was conducted at PT. Medan Technical Benefits located at Jl. Bogor No. 40 PasarBaru. Medan, Indonesia

DISCUSION

Test Normality

Normality Test is a test conducted with the aim of assessing the distribution of data in a group of data or variables, whether the distribution of data is distributed normally or not. The Normality Test is useful for determining data that has been collected in normal distribution or taken from normal populations. The classic method of testing the normality of a data is not so complicated.

Based on the empirical experience of some statisticians, data that amounts to more than 30 numbers ($n > 30$), it can be assumed to be normal distribution. It used to be said to be a large sample. But to provide certainty, data owned by normal distribution or not, should be used normality test. Because not necessarily data that is more than 30 can be ascertained as normal distribution, so on the contrary, data that amounts to less than 30 is not necessarily normal distribution, for that it needs a proof. To see if the distributed data is normal or not, the authors used a *Kolmogorov-Smirnov analysis test* with a significance value criteria to be greater than 0.05 to be said to be normal distributed data. Here are the test results:

Table 1. Normality Test Results

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test		
		Unstandardized Residual
N		30
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	0E-7
	Std. Deviation	1.31352115
	Absolute	.122
Most Extreme Differences	Positive	.086
	Negative	-.122
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		.670
Asymp, what's going on? Sig. (2-tailed)		.760
A. Test distribution is Normal.		
B. Calculated from data.		

Source: SPSS Output Version 20, Processed Data 2020

From the table of normality test results above, it is known that the significance value of 0.760 is greater than 0.05 so it can be concluded that the data tested is normally distributed.

Multicollinierity Test

Multicollinearity is a situation that indicates the existence of a correlation or strong relationship between two or more free variables in a multiple regression model. In the event of multicollinearity, then a variable that is strongly correlated with other variables in the model, the predictive strength is not reliable and unstable and the sense of multicollinearity is actually located in the presence or absence of correlation between free variables.

One way to see the presence or lack of symptoms of multicollinearity is to look at *the value of Tolerance* and *Variance Inflating Factor (VIF)*. If the *values Tolerance > 0.1* and *VIF < 10* can be indicated the existence of multicollinearity and vice versa. The following are the results of multicollinearity tests tested using *SPSS Version 20 software*.

Table 2. Multicollinierity Test Results

Coefficients ^a							
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	Q	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	Vif

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	(Constant)	1.031	2.074		.497	.623		
1	Conflict	.329	.083	.342	3.952	.001	.284	3.524
	Layoffs	.712	.093	.664	7.681	.000	.284	3.524
a. <i>Dependent Variable:</i> Spirit.Kerja								

Source: SPSS Output Version 20, Processed Data 2020

From the multi-covarity test result table above, it can be explained that *tolerance* value is $0.284 > 0.1$ and *VIF value* is $3,524 < 10$, respectively. These results show that there is no multi-covarity in the regression model.

Autocorrelation Test

Autocorrelation is a correlation between observation members arranged by time or place. A good regression model should not occur auto correlated. To see the autocorrelation in the regression model, the authors used the Durbin-Watson test with the following criteria:

1. Detection of Positive Autocorrelation:
 - a. If $dw < dL$ then there is a positive autocorrelation,
 - b. If $dw > dU$ then there is no positive autocorrelation,
 - c. If $dL < dw < dU$ then testing is inconclusive or inconclusive.
2. Detection of Negative Autocorrelation:
 - a. If $(4 - dw) < dL$ then there is a negative autocorrelation,
 - b. If $(4 - dw) > dU$ then there is no negative autocorrelation,
 - c. If $dL < (4 - dw) < dU$ then the test is inconclusive or inconclusive.

The following are the autocorrelation test results tested using SPSS Version 20 software.

Table 3. Autocorrelation Test Results

Model Summary ^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.971 ^a	.943	.938	1.36130	1.947
a. <i>Predictors:</i> (Constant), Layoffs, Conflict					
b. <i>Dependent Variable:</i> Spirit.Kerja					

Source: SPSS Output Version 20, Processed Data 2020

From the table of autocorrelation test results above, it can be found that the value of Durbin-Watson is 1,947 and the value is positive. To find out if the regression model in this study there is autocorrelation then it must be included in the test criteria as follows:

- $1,947 < 1,283$ then there is a positive autocorrelation (False)
- $1,947 > 1,566$ then no positive autocorrelation (True)
- $1,283 < 1,947 < 1,566$ then inconclusive testing (False)

Thus it can be concluded that autocorrelation testing in this study there is no positive autocorrelation.

Heteroscedasticity Test

Heteroscedasticity is an unlike residual variant on all observations within the regression model. Good regression should not occur heteroscedasticity. The heteroscedasticity test in this study was tested by graph method. The reason is because it is more practical, where when we do heteroscedasticity test, automatically the results of heteroscedasticity test can be immediately seen. Here are the results of heteroscedasticity test with graph method.

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Figure 1. Heteroskedastisity Test Results

Source: SPSS Output Version 20, Processed Data 2020

Scatter graph above clearly shows that there is no specific pattern because the irregular scattering point above and below the 0 axis on the Y axis.

Linear Regression

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

The results of multiple linear regression analysis can be seen in the table below:

Table 4.

Coefficients ^a							
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	Q	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	Vif
1	(Constant)	1.031	2.074	.497	.623		
	Conflict	.329	.083	.342	3.952	.284	3.524
	Layoffs	.712	.093	.664	7.681	.284	3.524

a. Dependent Variable: Spirit at work

Source: SPSS Output Version 20, Processed Data 2020

Multiple linear regression equations are obtained as follows:

$$Y = 1,031 + 0.329 X_1 + 0.712 X_2$$

1. Constant (a) = 1,031 indicates the constant value, where if the conflict variable (X₁) and the termination variable (X₂) = 0 then the employee's work spirit variable (Y) = 1,031.
2. The coefficient of regression of conflict variables (X₁) = 0.329 indicates that the conflict positively affects the employee's work force (Y), if the conflict (X₁) is raised by one unit then the employee's work spirit (Y) will also increase by 0.329.,

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- The regression coefficient of termination variable (X_2) = 0.712 indicates that the variable termination of employment has a positive effect on the employee's work spirit (Y), if the termination of employment (X_2) is increased by one unit then the employee's work spirit (Y) will also increase by 0.712.

Partial Hypothesis Test (t Test)

In the *table Coefficients^a obtained* also the value of t calculate. The value of the calculated t is then compared to the table $t_{\alpha} = 0.05$. The value of t table in df (n-k) where n is the number of samples and k is the number of variables both free and bound variables, then $30-3 = 27$. At df 27 with $\alpha = 0.05$ the table t value is 2,052.

The value of t calculate conflict variable (X_1) is 3,952, thus t calculate > t table, then H_0 is rejected and H_{1is} accepted which means that conflict variable (X_1) has a significant influence on employee work spirit (Y).

The value of t calculate the variable termination of employment (X_2) is 7,681, thus t calculate > t table, then H_0 is rejected and H_{1is} accepted which means that the termination variable (X_2) has a significant effect on the employee's work spirit (Y).

Simultaneous Hypothesis Test (Test F)

Anova or variant analysis is a joint regression coefficient test (F test) to test the significance of the influence of several independent variables on dependent variables. The results of the F test can be seen in the following table:

Table 5.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	822.765	2	411.383	221.992	.000 ^b
	Residual	50.035	27	1.853		
	Total	872.800	29			
a. Predictors: (Constant), Layoffs, Conflict						
b. Dependent Variable: Spirit.Kerja						

Source: SPSS Output Version 20, Processed Data 2020

In table Anova^b obtained calculated value F of 221,992 while the value of table F is 3.35. Thus F calculate > F table means variable conflict and termination of employment together have a positive and significant effect on the spirit of employee work (Y).

Determination Coefficient Test (R^2)

The coefficient of determination (R^2) of regression results can be seen in the table as below:

Table 5.

Model Summary ^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.971 ^a	.943	.938	1.36130	1.947
a. Predictors: (Constant), Layoffs, Conflict					
b. Dependent Variable: Spirit.at work					

Source: SPSS Output Version 20, Processed Data 2020

The coefficient of determination (R^2) of regression result of 0.943 means that the variable conflict and termination of employment contributes to the influence on the employee's work spirit (Y) of 94.3%. This result was the result of ($R^2 \times 100\%$), while the remaining 5.7% was influenced by other variables not studied in this study.

CONCLUSION

From the results of the research that has been discussed by processing the questionnaire data using several tests can be drawn conclusions as follows:

- In part, conflict variables (X_1) have a significant effect on the morale of employees (Y) in PT. Medan Technical Benefits. This means that the hypothesis in this study was accepted, proven from the value of t calculate > t table ($3,952 < 2,052$). While the variable termination of employment (X_2) has a significant influence on the work spirit of employees (Y) in PT. Medan

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Technical Benefits. This means that the hypothesis in this study was accepted, proven from the value of t calculate $> t$ table ($7,681 > 2,052$).

2. Simultaneously, conflict variables (X_1) and termination of employment (X_2) have a significant influence on employee morale (Y) in PT. Medan Technical Benefits. This means that the hypothesis in this study was accepted, as evidenced by the calculated F value $> F$ table ($221,992 > 3.35$).
3. Variable conflict (X_1) and termination of employment (X_2) were able to contribute influence to employee work spirit variable (Y) by 94.3% while the remaining 5.7% was influenced by other variables not researched in this study.

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